

Manufacturing Process-II
OPEN ENDED LAB

GROUP NO 01

SUBMITTED To:

Dr. Kashif Ishfaq

SUBMITTED By:

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Open-Ended Labs (OEL)

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Problem Statement of OEL

Manufacture a component for relevant/ standard application by choosing an appropriate machine tool & process parameters. State and evaluate important quality characteristics and submit the detailed working providing justification and comments.

Justification

The Honda CG125 experience abnormal engine noise and vibration due to excessive cam pin vibration. The engine starts making a strange noise, many people thinks that the problem is with camshaft, rocker and push rod, but the real problem is with cam pin due to its loose fitting and vibrations. The goal is to manufacturer a cam pin to reduce vibration which helps to stops it from shaking.

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Title

Manufacturing of Cam Pin using Aluminum

Literature View

Introduction:

A cam pin, also known as a timing pin or camshaft pin, is a cylindrical component used in the internal combustion engine of a motorcycle or other vehicles. It is typically, mounted on the camshaft. It often referred to as a dowel pin or lock pin, is a small, cylindrical piece of metal used to precisely align the camshaft and its gear assembly in an engine. [1]

Desired Part:

Fig.01: Cam Pin

Solid Work Design:

Fig.02: Cam Pin on Solid works

Fig.03: Views of Cam Pin

Importance of Cam Pin:

The camshaft cam pin is very important because it keeps the camshaft and the timing gear locked together in the right position. This makes sure the engine’s valves open and close at the correct time. Keeps the gear from slipping or moving out of place. Is important for the engine to run properly and safely.

The cam pin also reduce vibrations in the engine. If the cam pin is damaged or not functioned properly, the engine can run badly or not at all. Proper timing means better fuel efficiency and more power. [2]

Lathe Machine:

Lathe is a machine that is used to remove undesired material from work piece in form of chips with help of cutting tool. It rotates work piece about an axis of rotation to perform various operations like turning, facing, taper turning, knurling, drilling, boring, threading and parting to create an object with symmetry about that axis. It is also called universal lathe machine because of single point cutting tool and threading operation. [3,4]

Fig. 04: Lathe Machine [4]

Manufacturing Process for the Cam pin:

Following processes are used in manufacturing of cam pin.

- Facing
- Turning
- Drilling and Boring
- Parting
- Filing
- Vertical Milling

Facing

Facing is a machining operation on work piece using a lathe machine where tool removes material from end surface of a rotating work piece. The purpose of facing is to create smooth flat and level surface on the work piece often as a preparation for further operations. Proper control of cutting parameters, tool selection and correct techniques ensures that the operation achieves its goals without issues like poor surface finish. [5]

Mechanism

Facing is done by cross slider using nut and bolt mechanism. A nut and bolt mechanism refers to a type of mechanical fastener system used to join two or more parts together. It consists of two main components bolt and nut.

Turning

Turning is a common lathe operation where a cutting tool removes material from the outer diameter of a rotating work piece to achieve the desired size. This process is primarily used to create cylindrical or rounded parts and is one of the most common techniques in manufacturing. [6]

Mechanism

Turning is done by carriage using rack and pinion mechanism. It is a type of mechanical system used to convert rotational motion into linear motion. This mechanism is mostly used in steering systems in car, machine tools for precise linear movement etc.

Tool: High Speed Steel

High-speed steel (HSS) tools are cutting tools made from a special type of alloy steel that can maintain its hardness and wear resistance even at high temperatures. This allows them to cut materials at significantly faster speeds compared to traditional high-carbon steel tools. HSS tools are widely used in various applications like drill bits, milling cutters, and lathe tools. [7]

Fig. 05: HSS Tool [8]

Drilling

Drilling is a lathe operation of making a hole in a spinning piece of metal or other material. The work piece is fixed in the chuck and rotates, while the drill bit stays still and moves forward to cut the hole. This method is used to get a straight, centered hole, especially in round parts like rods or shafts. [8]

Tool: Drill Bit

A drill bit is a cutting tool fitted into a power drill to create holes in various materials like wood, metal, and concrete. It's essentially a rotating tool with a sharp tip that penetrates and removes material to form a hole. [9]

Fig. 06: Drill Bit Tool

Tool: Boring

A boring tool is a cutting tool used to enlarge and refine existing holes, typically after the hole has been created by drilling or other means. It is essentially a single-point cutting tool used in internal hole machining, hole enlargement, and contouring. [10]

Fig. 07: Boring Tool

Parting Operation:

Parting is used to separate a finished work piece from the larger piece of material it was originally cut from, like cutting off a piece of metal from longer bar. The tool makes progressive cut as the work piece rotates, gradually cutting through until the part is separated [11]

Fig. 08: Parting Tool

Drill Machine

A **drill machine** is a power-driven tool used to create round holes or drive fasteners into various materials such as wood, metal, plastic, or concrete. It operates by rotating a drill bit attached to a chuck, which is powered by an electric motor or other energy sources. [12]

Fig. 09: Drilling Machine [12]

Milling:

Milling is a machining process in which a rotating cutter removes material from a work piece, typically a metal or plastic, to shape it into the desired form. This process is commonly used for tasks like drilling, cutting, and shaping, and can be performed using a milling machine. [13]

Vertical Milling Machine:

A vertical milling machine is a tool used to cut and shape materials like metal, plastic, or wood. It has a spindle (the part that holds the cutting tool) that stands upright or vertically. The machine's head can move up and down, as well as side to side, to shape the material in different ways. [14]

Fig.10: Vertical Milling Machine [14]

Tool: End Cutter Mill

An end mill is a cutting tool used in milling machines to remove material from a work-piece. It has cutting edges on its end (tip) and sides, which makes it different from a drill (which only cuts at the tip). [15]

Fig.11: End Cutter Mill Tool [15]

Filing:

A filing operation usually means the process of smoothing, shaping, or removing small amounts of material from a work piece using a tool called a file. It's a common process in metalworking, woodworking, and even plastics. It removes sharp edges and smooth rough surfaces. [16]

Fig.12: Filing Tool [17]

Application of Cam Pin:

Following are applications of cam pin.

Fig.13: Cam Pin in a 125cc Engine

Fig.14: Cam Pin in Firearms (AR-15) [19]

- A cam pin is used in engines, especially in motorcycles, to keep the camshaft aligned with the crankshaft. It reduces unwanted vibrations by securing moving parts tightly. It ensures the engine's valves open and close at the right times. As shown in fig.13. [18]
- In AR-15 rifles, the cam pin is crucial for guiding the bolt's rotation during the locking and unlocking process. As shown in fig.14. [19]

Dimensions of Cam Pin:

Fig.15: Cam Pin Dimension on Solid Works

Material Selection:

The first step is to choose the right material. Aluminum is the third most common element comprising 8% of the earth crust. It is derived from mineral bauxite, which is converted into alumina using Bayer Process, then it is converted into aluminum metal using electrolytic cell. The Diameter is 25.5mm and length is 150.5mm. [20,3].

Fig.16: Work-piece

Table: 01 Composition of Aluminum 6061 [21]

Aluminum	Magnesium	Silicon	Copper	Chromium
97.9%	1.0%	0.6%	0.28%	0.2%

Table: 02 Properties of Material [3]

Property	Al
Density	2.6898 g/m ³
Melting Point	660.2°C
Boiling Point	2480°C
Young's modulus	68.3 MPa
Poisson's ratio	0.34
Yield strength	280 MPa
Ultimate strength	310 MPa

Machining Operation

Following are the machining operation given below:

- Facing and Turning
- Drilling and Boring
- Parting Operation
- Drill Machine
- Vertical Milling
- Filing

Facing

Fig.17: Facing Operation on lathe Machine with HSS Tool

Table:03 Facing Operation Parameters

Tool	RPM	Feed Rate (mm/min)	Depth of cut	Machining Time
High speed steel	590	0.05	Manually	0.50 sec

Explanation

In facing, HSS tool cut the material in a very short time around 0.50sec, with 590Rpm. It only clean or level the front surface of work-piece. It takes only one once and creates a flat surface.

Turning

Fig.18: Turning Operation with HSS Tool

Table:04 Turning Operation Parameters

Tool	RPM	Feed Rate (mm/min)	Depth of cut (mm)	Machining Time (sec)
High speed steel	590	0.05	2	47
			3	32
			3	32
			3	33
			1	93
			1.5	16
			0.5	47

Explanation

In turning operation, a rotating work-piece aluminum is cut by using HSS tool. The Tool moves while work-piece spin. Deeper cut takes less time but it can cause tool wear and vibrations while smaller cuts takes more time but good surface finish. The total time is 5min during whole process. At 1mm depth if cut machining time is 93sec while in 3mm depth of cut is 32sec. It takes 7 passes to form a desired part.

Drilling and Boring

Fig.19: Drilling Operation lathe Machine with Drill bit Tool

Table:05 Drilling Operation Parameters

Tool	RPM	Hole Length	Depth of cut	Machining Time
Drill Bit with Diameter (4.7mm)	590	33mm	Manually	1 min 8 sec

Explanation

The machining time for drilling with the lathe machine is 1min and 8sec, drill bit rotating with 590Rpm and drilling a hole of 33mm. A lower RPM can make the process slower and incorrect feed rate might cause too much pressure.

Fig.20: Drilling Operation lathe Machine with Drill bit Tool

Table:06 Drilling Operation Parameters

Tool	RPM	Hole Length	Depth of cut	Machining Time
Drill Bit with Diameter (0.8mm)	590	3mm	Manually	16 sec

Explanation

The machining time for drilling with the lathe machine is 16sec, drill bit rotating with 590Rpm and drilling a hole of 3mm whose diameter is 0.8mm

Fig.21: Drilling and Boring Operation lathe Machine with drill bit and Boring Tool

Table:07 Drilling and Boring Operation Parameters

Tool	RPM	Hole Length	Depth of cut	Machining Time
Drill Bit with Diameter (3.3mm)	590	10mm	Manually	21 sec
Boring Tool	590	-	Manually	34 sec

Explanation

Drilling is faster because its rough and remove material quickly while boring is slower because its precise and finish the hole with smoothness.

Parting Operation

Fig.22: Parting Operation on lathe Machine with Parting Tool

Drill Machine

Fig.23: Drilling Operation on Drill Machine with Drill Bit Tool

Table:08 Drilling Operation Parameters

Operation	Tool	Rpm	Feed Rate(mm/min)
Drilling on Drill Machine diameter (0.4mm)	Drill Bit	500	Manually

Vertical Milling

Fig.24: Vertical Milling Operation with End Mill Cutter Tool

Table:09 Vertical Milling Operation Parameters

Operation	Tool	Rpm	Feed Rate(mm/min)
Vertical Milling	End Mill cutter	475	Manually

Filing

Fig.25: Filing Operation

Responses

Cam Pin was made by using several machining operations. Although we tried to follow the original dimensions of cam pin but there is a slight difference in the final part. This may be due to manual feed control, small vibration in the machine during operation causes inaccuracy in dimensions, cutting may heat the aluminum which causes slightly expansion, which affect the final size while cooling down. During operation, small mistakes with operator can cause inaccuracy. The cam pin head is made using a vertical milling machine because it can easily cut flat surfaces and create slots. A lathe machine is good for making round parts, like the shaft of the pin, but it cannot create flat shapes or grooves. If the RPM or feed rate is not set correctly, it can cause problems. A higher RPM may speed up drilling but could cause overheating and wear out the tool faster.

Table:10 Percentage Error in Final Part

Part	Actual Length Dimension (mm)	Obtained Length Measurement (mm)	Error (mm)	% Error
For 12mm Diameter	8+2=10mm	9+1=10mm	0	0%
For 25mm Diameter	3+3+3=9mm	4.1+3.1+3.7=10.9	1.9	21.11%
Head Length	7mm	5.20mm	-1.80	25.71%
Total Length	56mm	56.1mm	0.10	0.18%

Result

The cam pin was successfully manufactured by using different operations including facing, turning, drilling, boring, with constant rpm 590, drilling with drill machine using 500 Rpm and vertical milling using 475 rpm. The overall manufactured part matches with original part but there is a slightly difference. The surface finish was acceptable.

Discussion

The dimension difference is due to upper part which is made up of vertical milling is 5.20mm but actual dimension is 7mm, similarly there is 0.5mm variation in some places which causes inaccuracy, may be material expand due to heating or may be due to human error while taking measurements. Similarly, obtained length is 0.1mm greater than the original length this may due to taking measurements during manufacturing of parts. The head length is 1.80mm smaller than the actual length.

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